

HOW TO IMPROVE ESSENTIAL LEADERSHIP QUALITIES IN CORPORATE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

This article explores methods to improve essential leadership qualities within the corporate sector, emphasizing that leadership skills can be cultivated rather than being innate. It discusses the importance of instilling leadership qualities in individuals from an early stage, such as during school and college education, through activities and projects. Leadership skills are critical for personal and professional growth, enabling individuals to face challenges, solve problems, and guide their careers. The article highlights the role of educational institutions, such as MIT Vishwashanti Gurukul, in nurturing leadership qualities through a holistic approach that includes imparting moral values and ethics.

Keywords: Communication skill, Collaboration and team spirit, Negotiation and cooperation skill, Planning and strategy development skill, Reading skill, Peer monitoring skill, Sense of responsibility

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SYNOPSIS

Leadership skill enhances the time management skills of the students. Students can plan their schedule accordingly. Students are able to achieve their goals in a better way through leadership skills

Context/Summary

“Leaders are born, not made” If you think the same, then you are wrong. Leaders can be created by instilling leadership skills in individuals. Leadership skill is one of the most important skills that can be acquired by the students in schools and colleges. It can be developed through various activities and projects organized in instituts.

There are many stages in life where leadership skills come into play. Life is full of challenges, employment issues and conflicts. In such situations, leadership skills enable students to accept challenges, solve problems and give a direction to their career. Leadership skill is not only important for student’s development, but it creates a great impact on the community, nation, companies, political scenario, nature and environment.

At MIT Vishwashanti Gurukul, top IB school in Pune, we aim at creating winning personalities. For this, we impart moral values, etiquettes and leadership skills in our students. Along with leadership skills, our students develop:

- 1.Communication skill
- 2.Collaboration and team spirit
- 3.Negotiation and cooperation skill
- 4.Planning and strategy development skill
- 5.Reading skill
- 6.Peer monitoring skill
- 7.Sense of responsibility

Importance of imparting leadership skills to students:

Leadership skill enhances the time management skills of the students. Students can plan their schedule accordingly. Students are able to achieve their goals in a better way through leadership skills. Students who possess leadership skills are aware of their rights and duties. They know how to get things done.

Those possessing leadership skills are team players. They know how to lead others. Leadership skill makes students more confident and they never hesitate in accepting challenges of life. Leadership skills help students to enhance their social skills. Students also learn how to communicate effectively.

Leadership skills help students to make better connections with others.Students possessing leadership skills are society-people. They have the ability to lead and find the solutions for problems like pollution, corruption, unemployment and social conflicts.

A school/college plays a pivotal role in instilling leadership skills in students. Here are some of the strategies that the school should adopt to impart leadership skills.By recognizing talent,

All the students have certain talent/skills that can turn them into a leader in a particular field. So, mentors must recognize the talent of individuals and help them to hone their skills.

Some of the students even possess leadership skill naturally. So, teachers should recognize them and encourage such students to sharpen their skills.

By Influencing: The teachers have a great influence on a student's life. Taking advantage of this influence, teachers should help the students to enhance their skill of leadership.

By Engaging them in Experiential Learning: The mentors should hone the leadership skills of the students by giving them projects and assignments that require teamwork. The teachers should encourage the students to organize and lead events in schools. It is through experiences that leaders can be created.

Extracurricular Activities: Extra-curricular activities play a significant role in developing leadership skill in students. Schools should organize such skills to instill leadership skills in students.

which maximises the efforts of others, towards the achievement of a goal. It has nothing to do with seniority or one's position in the hierarchy of a community or a group.

Confidence

Students who develop leadership skills learn to navigate challenges with confidence.

Communication

Leadership skills help students learn to express their ideas, collaborate with others, and build meaningful relationships.

Critical thinking

Leadership skills help students learn to make informed decisions and analyze situations from multiple perspectives.

Social skills

Leadership skills help students learn how to make better connections with others.

Teamwork

Leadership skills help students learn how to lead others and work as part of a team.

Career readiness

Leadership skills are highly sought-after in the professional world.

Time management

Leadership skills help students learn to balance their studies, personal lives, and extra-curricular activities.

Sense of responsibility

Leadership skills help students develop a strong sense of being able to take on responsibility and challenges.

Sense of maturity

Leadership skills help students develop a more profound sense of maturity.

Some activities that can help students develop leadership skills include:

Participating in class meetings, Joining team sports, Giving presentations, Conducting research Writing reports, Taking part in debates and elocutions, Listening to music Discussing presentations.

We see constant changes in communications and transportation, in new ways we access, create and share information, and in emerging enterprises that place consistent emphasis on new capabilities like critical and creative thinking and problem-solving. We also know climate change, new technologies, and an ever-changing geopolitical landscape, mean the future this current generation of children will inherit will be vastly different to our own. These things also mean our future world is open to boundless possibility for them. Navigating such rapid change requires confidence, adaptability and perseverance.

The Developing Skills For Life and Work report from the Young Foundation, The Australian Centre for Social Innovation and the Foundation for Young Australians, argues despite efforts to improve formal qualifications and work-based training, there is a growing consensus for more to be done to build the 'softer' skills which employers are increasingly seeking.

Young people who find their own voice in supportive school environments are more likely to develop a confident voice, a capacity to act in the world, and a willingness to lead others. By empowering students, we enhance student engagement and enrich their participation in the classroom, school and community.

Young people who are supported in harnessing their leadership skills are likely to gain a better understanding of themselves, a higher level of confidence, and an increased capacity to manage and organise their own lives. They are also likely to develop processes and skills useful in their learning and develop a more profound sense of maturity.

Student leaders go on to become independent thinkers who understand how to work as part of a team and have positive effects on organisations and communities.

Leadership Qualities Within the College Community

Schools come in different shapes and sizes and with various resources, but there is one resource that every school has: students. Students can be a great asset in shaping school culture and strengthening the connection between school and the wider community.

As adults, we often think of ourselves as the definitive architects of a college culture, but we misjudge the influence and effect students have on their own college community. There's something incredibly powerful in peer influence. Peers can quickly become role models and have the capacity to influence student values, attitudes and behaviours with an effectiveness school principals can only dream about. many schools, leadership positions are by election or appointment. Students who aren't interested in clubs or extracurricular activities they have to quit it immidiatly. leader can lead the team in successful direction he can chanalise the ideas finally only this skilled persons rule the society.

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